

Exploring the design and contributions of urban agroecosystem Living Labs for sustainable city development

Authors

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Abstract

Living Labs are open innovation ecosystems embedded in real-life settings, designed to tackle societal challenges through iterative, stakeholder-driven processes. Within the urban sustainability agenda, Urban Agroecosystem Living Labs (UALLs) have gained prominence for their role in transforming agri-food systems and enhancing urban resilience. This study examines the design and contributions of UALLs based on a content analysis of cases reported in academic and grey literature. Six UALLs were identified, revealing considerable diversity in their objectives, operational processes, activities, and participant configurations. Beyond improving food security and agricultural productivity, UALLs contribute to sustainable urban transitions by fostering responsible consumption, enhancing community cohesion, increasing urban greening and biodiversity, reducing waste, and supporting climate mitigation efforts. The RUBA Initiative (led by Ean University in Colombia) exemplifies a comprehensive UALL model that integrates ecological, economic, and social dimensions. Despite their potential, most UALLs lack explicit alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and often fall short in measuring long-term impact. This paper underscores the need to strengthen evaluation frameworks, adopt SDG-based indicators, and improve scalability. Ultimately, it advocates for the broader adoption of UALLs as adaptable platforms capable of advancing systemic change towards sustainable and inclusive urban futures.

Key words

Living lab, co-creation; innovation, stakeholders, SDGs, circular economy, sustainable future.

Introduction

Urban development has followed uneven and unsustainable patterns, producing socio-environmental disparities across city cores, suburbs, and peri-urban areas (Antwi-Afari et al., 2021; Bibri, 2021; Riaño-Herrera, Varela-Martínez, et al., 2023). This fragmentation has compromised the management of key natural resources and exacerbated challenges such as land degradation, food system waste, biodiversity loss, and climate change (The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OCDE), 2012; Y. Wang et al., 2019). In response, resilient and sustainable urban models are increasingly promoted as necessary frameworks for balancing human development with ecological integrity (Azunre et al., 2019; Slater & Birchall, 2022).

Two urban strategies have gained prominence in this context: agroecosystem-based approaches that strengthen urban food resilience, and integrative models that connect urban and rural agri-food systems (Debrah et al., 2022; Riaño-Herrera, Romero-Perdomo, et al., 2023; J. Wang et al., 2024). These efforts are aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDGs 2, 11, and 12, which advocate for zero hunger, sustainable cities, and responsible consumption (United Nations, 2023).

In support of such transitions, Living Labs have emerged as experimental platforms fostering open, transdisciplinary innovation through real-world co-creation and iterative feedback (Cilliers et al., 2014; Dawodu et al., 2022). Living Labs serve as bridges between science, policy, community, and industry, advancing solutions grounded in circular economy, bioinspiration, and nature-based systems (McPhee et al., 2021; Steen & van Bueren, 2017). Among them, Urban Agroecosystem Living Labs (UALLs) focus on reducing urban ecological footprints by transforming agri-food systems through collaboration between farmers, researchers, institutions, and communities (Brons et al., 2022; García-Llorente et al., 2019; Thees et al., 2020).

Despite their potential, the role of UALLs in urban sustainability remains insufficiently documented, particularly in the Global South (McPhee et al., 2021). In Colombia, where malnutrition and food insecurity persist, public-private coordination has been limited, and urban food strategies remain underdeveloped (Ponce et al., 2023; Vargas-Carpintero et al., 2023; World Food Programme, 2024). To address this, EAN University launched the

RUBA Initiative, the first UALL in the country, which promotes regenerative agriculture, small-scale food production, and interdisciplinary collaboration to advance sustainable city models (Riaño-Herrera, Varela-Martínez, et al., 2023).

This study explores the current landscape of UALLs, their design characteristics, and their contributions to sustainable urban development. It responds to two core questions: (i) Which UALLs are documented in academic and grey literature? and (ii) How are UALLs designed in terms of aims, iterative processes, activities, participants, SDG alignment, and urban sustainability impacts? Additionally, it identifies barriers and provides actionable recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness and replicability of UALLs.

Materials and methods

Identification of UALLS

A review of academic and grey literature was conducted to identify existing UALLs, followed by a content analysis examining aspects of their design and contributions. The academic literature review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) protocol (Moher et al., 2009). This process comprised four stages (see Table 1). First, the parameters for the literature search were established to ensure a uniform approach. To reduce bias from database updates, all searches were completed in a single day. Second, a thorough collection of publications was identified. The search query was crafted based on suggestions by Leal Filho et al. (2022) and Hossain et al. (2019) and applied to two primary databases: Scopus and Web of Science (WoS). These databases are acknowledged as reliable sources of peer-reviewed publications by leading researchers (Ogunmakinde et al., 2022). Third, publications were filtered according to two criteria (document type and language). Finally, a comprehensive content screening – guided by the questions “Are Agroecosystem Living Labs mentioned?” and “Do these Living Labs operate in urban areas?” – was conducted to verify the relevance of each publication, resulting in the selection of 15 relevant publications. In addition, 13 grey literature documents were included from authoritative sources such as the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), the Living Labs Federation, and the Australian Living Labs Innovation Network (ALLiN), ensuring practical cases were considered alongside academic ones (Bouma, 2022; Bouma & Veerman, 2022; Cooke et al., 2021; Della Santa et al., 2024; García-Llorente et al., 2019; Laborgne et al., 2021; McPhee et al., 2021; Pearson, 2021; Ponce et al., 2023; Potters et al., 2022; Santonen et al., 2022; Säumel et al., 2019; Tiwari et al., 2022; Yan & Roggema, 2019).

Table 1. PRISMA protocol steps to identify reported UALLs.

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STEPS	CRITERION	OUTPUTS
Parameter definition	Search query	("living lab*") AND ((agr* AND ecosyst*) OR agroecosystem) in Title, Abs, Keywords
	Time horizon	No limit
	Search date	12 June 2025
	Database	Scopus
Identification	Number of publications through database searching	n = 50
Screening	Exclusion: 1. books, book chapters, notes, tutorials, conference papers, short surveys, no abstract, errata	Records excluded n= 7
	2. Language other than English	Full-text articles consolidated: n= 43
	3. Duplicated publications between databases	
Eligibility	Exclusion reasons (not related to the topic)	Selected academic literature papers: n = 13

Aspects to be examined in UALLs

To examine UALL design and contributions, we developed a matrix assessing six key components:

- (i) **Aims:** The primary mission guiding each UALL, grouped into three categories: (A1) focusing on the sustainability and resilience of agriculture and agri-food systems; (A2) emphasizing tangible innovation through technology, improved management practices or processes; and (A3) prioritising knowledge generation and the creation of knowledge networks (McPhee et al., 2021b). Sustainability can be fostered through locally tailored agricultural practices that address the needs of farmers and other stakeholders, yielding economic, social, and environmental benefits. Resilience can be enhanced by strengthening the adaptive capacity of agricultural and agri-food systems, enabling them to better withstand and recover from shocks and stresses such as climate change or market fluctuations. (McPhee et al., 2021b)
- (ii) **Iterative process:** The participatory, transdisciplinary, and continuous improvement nature of UALLs (and Living Labs in general). Steen and van Bueren (2017) propose that the living lab innovation process comprises five broad stages: (IP1) research, (IP2) development, (IP3) testing, (IP4) implementation, and (IP5) commercialisation

of a developed product. Research involves reviewing existing knowledge to gain insight and inform decisions. Development focuses on generating, refining, and modifying a product to improve its complexity or functionality. Testing entails evaluating a product's performance through practical application. Implementation is the deployment of a final product in a real-world environment. Finally, commercialisation involves marketing the developed product, requiring efforts to persuade users who were not involved in its creation. These stages are guided by studies on innovation processes for new product development, agile methodologies, and user-driven open innovation (Beck et al., 2001; Cooper, 1988; Mikkela, 2008; von Hippel, 2005). Importantly, these phases are not strictly linear and are frequently iterative.

- (iii) **Activities:** ALL activities reflect co-development, co-production, and co-creation within the complex landscape of agricultural and agri-food systems. These activities address economic, social, and environmental realities through measurement, evaluation, and both qualitative and quantitative methods. McPhee et al. (2021) identify the following types of activities: (ACT1) data management and analysis; (ACT2) innovation cycles marked by high uncertainty due to external factors; and (ACT3) dissemination and scaling of documented findings. The development of these activities must be closely linked to iterative processes and consider the influence of ecological processes in agriculture.
- (iv) **Participants:** Agriculture and agri-food systems involve a wide variety of stakeholders with diverse values and interests, leading to complex interactions among researchers, officials, businesses, producers, consumers, farmers, and citizens. Participants can be grouped into four categories: (PT1) those in the public or governmental sector; (PT2) users whose roles may change over time; (PT3) individuals from business or academic institutions; and (PT4) a broad spectrum of partners with varying interests and beliefs, necessitating complex governance structures (McPhee et al., 2021). Addressing challenges in agri-food systems requires collaborative efforts that involve interdisciplinary or even transdisciplinary approaches, supported by governance frameworks capable of managing such complexities.
- (v) **SDGs:** We examined whether the identified UALLs explicitly referenced the UN SDGs. The limited literature on this topic suggests that Living Labs, including UALLs, have the potential to advance the United Nations' 2030 Agenda by focusing on innovation and sustainable development (Leal Filho, Caughman, et al., 2022). We checked whether each UALL source explicitly mentioned any of the 17 SDGs.

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- (vi) **Contributions:** To understand how UALLs aid the transition to sustainable cities, we applied three sustainability criteria: (C1) environmental management integrated with land-use planning, (C2) encouragement of sustainability-focused lifestyles, and (C3) improvement of environmental quality through community engagement (Aparicio et al., 2024; Karal & Soyer, 2024; Rachmawati et al., 2024; Sodiq et al., 2019).
- **Environmental management integrated with land-use planning:** Effective urban environmental management incorporates economic, social, and ecological elements alongside local needs. This includes rehabilitating ecosystems, optimising land use, and strengthening links between urban and surrounding areas to ensure the provision of ecosystem services. Inclusive spatial planning and participatory governance are crucial, supported by nature-based solutions (e.g., urban forests, green corridors) and circular strategies such as recycling and waste minimisation (Aparicio et al., 2024; Karal & Soyer, 2024; Rachmawati et al., 2024; Slater & Birchall, 2022; Sodiq et al., 2019).
 - **Encouragement of sustainability-focused lifestyles:** Urban sustainability depends not only on infrastructure but also on changes in daily behaviours. Encouraging responsible consumption, sustainable transportation, and civic engagement requires educational initiatives that reshape collective values around equity, environmental awareness, and well-being. These changes are essential to reconfiguring the social and cultural foundations of urban life (Aparicio et al., 2024; Karal & Soyer, 2024; Rachmawati et al., 2024; Riaño-Herrera, Romero-Perdomo, et al., 2023; Slater & Birchall, 2022; Sodiq et al., 2019; Yan & Roggema, 2019).
 - **Environmental quality through community engagement:** Ensuring environmental quality in cities relies on both technical metrics (e.g., water availability, air quality, green spaces) and on how communities perceive and engage with their environment. Empowering residents through environmental education, participatory monitoring, and collaborative restoration enhances their agency, social cohesion, and sense of belonging – all vital for achieving long-term ecological benefits (Reijneveld et al., 2024; Slater & Birchall, 2022; Sodiq et al., 2019; Yan & Roggema, 2019).

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Figure 1. UALL characterization matrix. It was designed based on (McPhee et al., 2021; Steen & van Bueren, 2017)

Results

A review of the academic and grey literature revealed a total of 34 Urban Agroecosystem Living Labs (UALLs) located in various countries, including the Netherlands, Norway, Italy, Spain, Belgium, Germany, France, Turkey, Kenya, Nigeria, Thailand, Canada, Cuba, and Colombia. Several of these initiatives also serve rural communities and some UALLs are part of national or international networks, but in many cases no official website or published description could be found.

Aims

The UALLs demonstrated that they address all three categories of aims. Among them, the Almería Agroecology Living Lab was the only one tackling all three goals. Its efforts focus first on promoting active stakeholder participation and learning through a Nexus approach that links the complex relationships between water, energy, and food production. Secondly, it implements a demonstration programme for farmers, equipping them with knowledge and strategies to improve farming practices and establish a collaborative knowledge network. Ultimately, it encourages sustainable agricultural methods.

Five UALLs pursue two of the three aim categories: AgriLink's Living Lab, AU/LAB Centre for Co-creation, Bio Danubius Hub, L'Acadie Lab (Innovation Ouverte pour l'Agriculture Urbaine), and the RUBA Living Lab. In particular, RUBA's aims are pursued through six thematic areas: (i) efficient water resource management; (ii) deployment of renewable photovoltaic energy; (iii) resilience and conservation of urban soils; (iv) implementation of organic and regenerative agriculture; (v) transformation of urban food consumption patterns; and (vi) development of low-cost technological innovations for small- and medium-scale producers.

These integrated strategies reflect RUBA's commitment to systemic innovation and respond to acute urban challenges such as food insecurity and socio-economic vulnerability. Among the other UALLs, the Territorial Innovation Laboratory and the AU/LAB Centre for Co-creation stand out. While sustainability receives more attention than resilience across cases, there is a disparity among sustainability's three dimensions: compared to environmental and economic aspects, the social dimension has received less emphasis.

The second most frequently emphasised aim is tangible innovation in technology, management practices, or processes. This includes advancements in eco-technologies like renewable energy and artificial intelligence, and the design of flexible food production systems. Notable examples include Agrotopia Living Lab, Bio Danubius Hub, and Mezopotamya Living Lab. The least common aim is knowledge generation and network creation. For instance, the Urban Farm at Toronto Metropolitan University's Living Lab aims to facilitate ecosystem innovation by conducting research projects on rooftop agriculture integrated with green roof technology.

Iterative process

Overall, the phases most often implemented were research (n = 11) and development (n = 11), followed by testing (n = 10), implementation (n = 9), and commercialisation (n = 5). Only two UALLs – the AU/LAB Centre for Co-creation and Innovation Ouverte pour l’Agriculture Urbaine, and Occitanum – fully integrated all five iterative phases. Close behind, Agrotopia Living Lab, Territorial Innovation Laboratory, and U-Garden implemented four of the five phases. In contrast, 14 UALLs were poorly documented regarding their iterative processes, describing only one or none of the phases. This lack of systematisation and strengthening of iterative processes was notably observed in UALLs within the INVEST network (e.g., the Living Labs of Central-Southern Region, North Karelia, Larissa, Friesland and Gelderland, Peatland Area Friesland, De Achterhoek, Delta East, and Nitra). Although these labs have clear purpose-oriented goals, their iterative processes remain underdeveloped.

Activities

The UALLs engaged in three main types of activities. The most prevalent, observed in over one-third of the UALLs, is the effort to expand and scale the findings from their projects. For example, L’Acadie Lab collaborates on watershed management projects for the Acadie River through experimentation and co-creation, generating new ideas for agroecosystem rehabilitation by enhancing or implementing new practices and technologies. Similarly, the ILVO Agri-Food Technology Living Lab provides a workshop setting where sensors are validated, prototypes are developed, data is processed, and solutions are tested. These tests occur in real-world facilities like trial fields, greenhouses, and barns, enabling practical evaluation of improved or new processes.

The second most common activity involves innovation cycles characterised by high levels of uncertainty due to external variables. For instance, Agrotopia Living Lab uses an open innovation method in an iterative process to explore new applications of knowledge and technologies in urban horticulture and greenhouses. Likewise, the Urban Farm at TMU’s Living Lab employs the living lab model to foster innovation, co-creation, and user participation, focusing on developing an effective rooftop agriculture solution tested under real-world conditions. Across the board, UALLs identified climate factors and stakeholder engagement as the critical external variables contributing to uncertainty in innovation cycles.

Lastly, data management and analysis are activities associated with UALLs that focus on evaluating prototypes, infrastructure, and cutting-edge technologies. This is the case for

the ILVO Agri-Food Technology Living Lab, the RUBA Living Lab, the Living Lab at the Monterrey Institute of Technology, and the Vrouwe Vennepolder Living Lab. For example, RUBA emphasises data management and the analysis of water and soil, in addition to scaling up its research findings.

Participants

Most UALLs provided limited detail about their participants, often only stating the use of a multidisciplinary approach without clarifying the specific types or roles of those involved. This implies that UALLs involve not only farmers but also a broad array of stakeholders across the agriculture and agri-food system, with the specific mix shaped by each lab's local context. Overall, UALLs engaged all categories of participants, though public-sector stakeholders were the least frequently mentioned. The broadest diversity of participants was seen in U-Garden, followed by the Dutch Living Lab ENaBLEs. Typically, UALLs included two main participant categories: users whose roles can evolve over time, and individuals from business or academic organisations – as observed in the Nairobi and Makueni Living Labs, Occitanum, and ILVO, among others.

Association with the SDGs

Apart from RUBA, none of the UALLs showed an explicit connection to the SDGs. Although several UALLs address issues relevant to multiple SDGs, they did not explicitly mention the goals. In contrast, the RUBA Living Lab demonstrates how Living Labs can intentionally align with and operationalise the SDGs. RUBA aims to contribute to SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 4 (Quality Education), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and SDG 13 (Climate Action) as part of its core design. This strategic alignment drives its efforts to transform Bogotá into a sustainable urban hub through interdisciplinary collaboration, resource optimisation, and community empowerment.

Contribution to the sustainable development of cities

The most common type of contribution among the UALLs was a combination of environmental management with territorial planning ($n = 8$), followed by contributions to environmental quality and community wellbeing ($n = 7$), and finally the promotion of sustainability-oriented lifestyles ($n = 4$). None of the UALLs in our review achieved contributions across all three categories. However, four UALLs reported impacts in two categories: the Vrouwe Vennepolder Living Lab, L'Acadie Lab, ILVO Agri-Food Technology Living Lab, and RUBA Living Lab. The remaining 24 UALLs reported contributions in only one category or none.

Discussion

Understanding and spread of UALLs

Some initiatives may have been mislabelled as UALLs due to an overemphasis on multi-sector collaboration or conventional knowledge-sharing rather than true co-creation. Comparable findings indicate that governance is a pivotal factor in enabling successful innovation in Living Labs. Effective governance entails fostering interaction, building trust, and providing training in co-creation techniques. Empowering stakeholders and valuing their contributions are essential to effectively advance innovation and positive change. To safeguard the credibility, distinctiveness, and effectiveness it is imperative to uphold their key, non-negotiable attributes: functioning as innovation platforms, employing a user-centered approach, prioritising co-creation and knowledge sharing, operating in real-life contexts, engaging diverse stakeholders, and applying iterative processes (Lévesque et al., 2023). Despite some conceptual variance among cases, the adoption of UALLs is expected to become more widespread and conceptually clearer, thereby strengthening agricultural knowledge and innovation systems (Potters, Schoorlemmer, et al., 2022).

The study also shows that UALLs are being implemented in multiple cities worldwide, predominantly in developed countries. This aligns with Cascone et al., (2024), who noted a high concentration of Living Labs in Europe, and suggests that sustainability and innovation transitions are often framed in a North–South context (Wieczorek, 2018). This pattern raises the question of how to encourage the expansion of UALLs to other regions of the world. International and national networks are instrumental for disseminating case studies and providing implementation guidance to Living Labs led by governments, universities, and companies. One of the most influential is the European Network of Living Labs, which has inspired the creation of similar networks such as the Brazilian Network of Living Labs (Living Labs Brasil, 2023). This underscores the need for greater international collaboration and knowledge exchange to maximise mutual learning opportunities and generate innovative solutions with global reach through Living Labs.

Outside Europe, UALL initiatives in South America and Africa are limited. RUBA remains the only documented UALL in South America, serving as a key reference for future development (Circular Bioeconomy Alliance, 2024; Guerra & Syed, 2024). By contrast, African countries have more UALL and agroecosystem Living Lab initiatives, driven by transdisciplinary projects like HealthyDiets4Africa, which embrace the Living Lab model to co-create and scale food system innovations with diverse stakeholders – thereby improving food and nutrition security (HD4A., 2025).

UALL design

Our findings indicate that UALLs should strengthen knowledge production and dissemination through innovation. Their transdisciplinary approach fosters networks that transcend regional boundaries, creating broader international linkages. To remain effective, UALLs must align with diverse stakeholder interests, ensure sustained engagement, and leverage technology to drive innovation. Gardezi et al., (2024) emphasise that Living Labs can address the human and social dimensions of technological adoption and agricultural innovation. Nevertheless, a persistent challenge for Living Labs – especially in developing countries – is securing consistent funding. Conventional research funding cycles (often under five years) are typically insufficient for the long-term nature of Living Lab initiatives. This underscores the importance of developing more sustainable financial models to ensure their operation and success.

The iterative processes of UALLs reveal a fragmented application of the five phases of innovation cycles. This unevenness may hinder the development of high-value territorial innovation models, limiting adaptability, scalability, and transferability. While some initiatives show operational maturity, many UALLs remain focused mainly on the development phase. A persistent challenge is the active engagement of stakeholders in co-creation and design thinking. This suggests the need for a structured tool or framework to guide farmers and other stakeholders through the various stages of the process (Fuglsang et al., 2021; Gardezi et al., 2024). Additionally, current understanding remains limited regarding the conditions under which Living Labs can effectively contribute to the development of agricultural knowledge and innovation systems (Potters, Collins, et al., 2022).

Regarding activities, von Wirth et al., (2019) identify six approaches to facilitate the dissemination of innovations and knowledge developed in Living Labs: creating transformative spaces, mobilising network partners, replicating the lab framework elsewhere, providing education and training, stimulating business development, and using narratives to convey contributions. This encourages Living Lab managers to critically consider the intended contributions of their innovation cycles. Within data analysis and management activities, evidence suggests that Living Labs can capture the mindsets of actors involved in sustainability transformations. For example, Guerra and Syed (2024) identified three prevailing mindsets among actors in urban climate governance in Argentina, Brazil, and Mexico: the sceptical activist, the optimistic technocrat, and the ambivalent spectator. These mindsets encompass the emotions,

beliefs, values, perceptions, attitudes, and worldviews that influence behaviours across various actors, from policymakers to often marginalised community groups.

Our findings emphasize the need for UALLs to systematically map stakeholder relationships and interaction dynamics. While Living Labs aim to foster participation and inclusive decision-making through cross-sector collaboration, their effectiveness may be limited if key actors fail to integrate experimental outcomes into broader urban transition frameworks (Potters, Collins, et al., 2022). It is therefore critical to identify strengths (such as effective collaboration and stakeholder synergies) as well as capacity gaps (such as mismatches, conflicts, resource inefficiencies, and challenges in coordinating multi-stakeholder processes) (Cascone et al., 2024).

SDGs and sustainable contribution to cities

Our qualitative analysis shows that nearly all UALLs lack alignment with the SDGs. This disconnect can result in interventions that are not sustainable, potentially creating new trade-offs or exacerbating existing ones. This finding contrasts with Leal Filho et al. (2022), who found that most of 20 Living Labs studied concentrated on SDGs 4 (Quality Education) and 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities). Meanwhile, Reijneveld et al. (2024) suggests that UALLs should broaden their scope, contributing to SDGs related to water, energy, climate action and biodiversity. Given these differences, it is essential to evaluate and monitor Living Labs to better understand their impact on the SDGs.

UALLs are increasingly recognized as important platforms for urban transformation, expanding from their original focus on agri-food production to broader urban sustainability issues. They help build sustainable cities by encouraging mindful food consumption, strengthening community resilience, expanding urban greening and biodiversity, creating green jobs, and aiding efforts to combat climate change (European Network Living Labs (ENoLL), 2023; García-Llorente et al., 2019; Living Labs Federation, 2023; McPhee et al., 2021; Ponce et al., 2023). However, challenges such as soil contamination, resource overuse and biodiversity loss persist, highlighting the need for locally adapted mitigation strategies. (Brohmer et al., 2023).

Promoting sustainable lifestyles involves addressing cultural barriers between generations, as changing established habits and values challenging (Trivellas et al., 2023). Living Labs should collaborate in these efforts, since transforming consumption patterns and adopting responsible practices can enhance the impact of sustainability transitions and promote greater resilience in urban environments (Marselis et al., 2024).

A key issue is that the majority of UALLs report their contributions in qualitative terms, often lacking robust indicators or consistent long-term monitoring Lévesque et al. (2023) recommend combining qualitative methods like interviews and storytelling with quantitative approaches and conventional indicators to improve evaluation.

Recommendations

This study offers several recommendations for future UALL initiatives, which can generally be applied to the Living Lab model. It is crucial to consider that each suggestion should be tailored to regional conditions and development contexts:

- First, we advise strengthening the promotion, establishment, and funding of Living Labs (including UALLs) as cultural catalysts for sustainable development across public, private, academic, and non-governmental sectors. National and regional initiatives or networks could foster collaboration, financial support, strategic alignment, and continuous improvement of Living Labs' mission. Furthermore, their integration into corporate social responsibility programs and innovation frameworks, such as the “quintuple helix” (academia, industry, civil society, government, and the environment). These approaches reflect evolving dynamics in knowledge creation and the promotion of sustainable development, aspects increasingly required in funding calls by government science and innovation agencies.
- Second, we recommend establishing a structured process for identifying and engaging participants. This strategy will yield benefits through iterative processes and activities that are well-aligned with the local context. It will also require new methods of consensus-building to tackle challenges and pinpoint areas for improvement. Brohmer et al. (2023) emphasise the importance of avoiding selection bias by involving participants beyond the “usual suspects” (i.e., not only the technologically proficient or forward-thinking individuals. Beaudoin et al (2022) advocate approaches that focus on creating, managing, and exchanging urban commons, both tangible (like food or the environment) and intangible (like shared values and ideas). In this way, individuals gain experience and become more actively involved in shaping the future of their city. It is crucial to promote synergies among urban Living Labs, sustainable development initiatives, and city planning.
- Third, while UALLs address technical aspects of agroecosystem innovation, we recommend implementing advanced sustainability tools and practices to strengthen the innovation and resilience of their activities. Tools such as circular economy principles, nature-based solutions, life cycle assessment, multi-criteria analysis, and sustainable value mapping and analysis (SVMA) can help drive socio-ecological

systemic change in cities (Beaudoin et al., 2022; Riaño-Herrera, Romero-Perdomo, et al., 2023; Romero-Perdomo & González-Curbelo, 2023; Villagrán et al., 2024; Winans et al., 2021). Additionally, UALLs should move beyond technical solutions to address the behaviours, habits, and social patterns that contribute to the complexity of urban agroecosystems.

- Fourth, UALLs should track their impact over time using a variety of metrics and adjust strategies based on the outcomes. Possible metrics include the volume of local food production, air quality indices, urban carbon footprint, urban biodiversity levels, food waste reduction, local food security status, urban poverty rates, climate resilience indicators, the economic value of ecosystem services, technology adoption rates, and the cultural or landscape value of the city (Bibri, 2021; De Marco & Mangano, 2021; Riaño-Herrera, Varela-Martínez, et al., 2023; J. Wang et al., 2024). By doing so, UALLs can more clearly demonstrate their role in promoting sustainable urban development.

The importance of the United Nations SDGs for Living Labs is clear, and UALLs have significant potential to support their achievement. We strongly recommend that UALLs link their activities to specific SDGs, using them as a roadmap for a holistic approach to social, economic, and environmental sustainability. Achieving the SDGs locally is complex and requires structured processes within a governance framework, rather than isolated efforts (Artmann & Sartison, 2018; Corsi et al., 2023; Leal Filho, Caughman, et al., 2022; Leal Filho et al., 2023). The work by McPhee et al. (2021) provides useful indicators and perspectives to help ensure that UALL contributions have impact beyond the local scale.

Conclusions

This study examines the status and possible impacts of UALLs in promoting the transition to sustainable cities. UALLs are defined by their varied aims, iterative processes, activities and participant engagement. This diversity creates an opportunity for cross-learning, allowing UALLs to enhance their frameworks by leveraging the strategies and insights of others. Additionally, the characterization framework applied in this research provides valuable input for designing future UALLs.

Two key areas that need attention in the design of UALLs are the structure of the iterative process and the level of participant engagement. Current methods for identifying and involving stakeholders lack sufficient organization and there is inadequate focus on the social contributions of UALLs. Despite these challenges, UALLs demonstrate potential in fostering civic engagement, responsible consumption, ecological initiatives, climate

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action and food waste reduction, positioning them as a pathway for supporting sustainable urban development. However, their alignment with the SDGs and the lack of robust metrics to evaluate long-term impact remain shortcomings. The role of UALLS should extend beyond immediate outcomes, targeting measurable, long-term systemic changes that can be sustained within communities and regions. Achieving this requires a collaborative effort from all stakeholders, who must adapt their practices to implement models capable of producing significant and systemic transformations.

Although this paper focuses on UALLs and sustainable cities, the findings are relevant to all Urban Living Labs. Integrating UALLs with urban planning is a long-term challenge and future research is needed to improve their contributions and define success criteria. Furthermore, it is highly recommended to empirically validate the findings presented here to inform future UALL initiatives.

This study has several limitations: it did not fully assess the Living Lab model or specific urban contexts; it only included UALLs documented in literature and major networks, possibly excluding others and limited information from official websites restricted analysis. Despite these limitations, the study offers valuable insights for developing a more cohesive framework for UALL design, moving beyond ad hoc approaches.

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